

Fatty acid composition of some minor seed oils from arid zone of Rajasthan

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Fatty acid compositions of seed oils of eight species belonging to six different less familiar botanical families are reported. All the seeds were collected from arid zone of Rajasthan State and examined for their physicochemical characteristics and fatty acid composition. Out of these one has been reinvestigated and the fatty acid composition was compared with the earlier results.

Characteristics of eight plant species are depicted in Table 1. The physicochemical characteristics of their seeds and oils are presented in Table 2. The presence of an unusual function or any oxygenated function was ruled out on the basis of UV, IR spectra and TLC techniques. All the species reported were found to contain high percentage of C₁₈-unsaturated acids, among which oleic and linoleic acids were dominating. The combined unsaturated acids were 52.82–80.9% high oleic acid content was noticed for species sl. nos. 3, 4, 8, 2 and 5 (Table 1) as 31.2, 27.5, 26.8, 25.0 and

24.7% respectively. Linolenic acid was present in all the species but as a major component in species sl. no. 2 (30.6%). The combined contents of linoleic and linolenic acids (PUFA) was found in varying amounts in species sl. nos. 1, 5, 3, 4, 8, 2 and 7 as 32.3, 35.6, 36.8, 37.1, 51.7, 54.3 and 54.9%, respectively. The range of total saturated fatty acids is 20.6–38.4% and the varying proportion of these acids was 38.4, 37.1, 34.5, 30.6, 27.8, 25.23, 21.4 and 20.6% in species sl. nos. 5, 1, 4, 3, 7, 6, 8 and 2, respectively. Among these acids palmitic acid was the

Table 1. Identification of plants*

Sl. no.	Name	Family	Local name	Shape, size, availability	Flowering and fruiting	Characteristics of seed
1.	<i>Cleome viscoa</i>	Copparaceae	<i>BogrolHandi-bagro</i>	Erect, glandular pubescent, annual herb, 1-9 dm high hairy steam	July-Oct.	1.5 mm dia, brown-black
2.	<i>Barleria acarnthoides</i>	Acanthaceae	<i>Bajardanti Chapari</i>	Harsh, prickly, branched under shrub, 30 cm high	Sept.-Nov.	1.2 cm long compressed silky hairy, ovoid
3.	<i>Mimosa hamata</i> ^a	Mimosaceae	<i>Jinajani</i>	Much branched, armed shrub	Aug.-Nov. Dec.-Feb.	6 × 4 mm, chestnut brown
4.	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> ^a	Mimosaceae	<i>Kolai</i>	Rigid, much branched, thorny shrub	Aug.-Nov.	4.6 × 3-4.5 mm, deep brown, glossy
5.	<i>Argyrea nervosa</i>	Convolvulaceae	<i>Ghavbel</i>	Large climber, grown in public places	Aug.-Nov.	0.5 mm, spherical white-grey.
6.	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> ^a	Fabaceae	<i>Koyalri</i>	Twining perennial with few branches	July -Nov. Apr.-June	Black, smooth, oblong
7.	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> ^a	Fabaceae	<i>Biyani Sarphanko</i>	Much branched perennial herb 6-8 dm high	July-Dec.	5-6 seeds in recurved soft pod
8.	<i>Sesamam mulayanum</i>	Pedaliaceae	<i>Til</i>	Erect, glandular, pubescent annual herb	Aug.-Oct.	Rugose veined, dark-brown

*All seeds are collected by hands during December-March.

^a Oil content is less than 10%.

Table 2 Analytical data on seeds and oils

Species	Oil %	Protein %	Moist-ure%	RI 30 nD	I.V.	% Unsap	S.V.	Methyl ester composition (%) of oil					
								16 : 0	18 : 0	18 : 1	18 : 2	18 : 3	Others
<i>C. viscosa</i>	9.6	NX 6.25 34.0	4.6	1.4668	90	1.8	198	29.90	14.60	20.50	30.40	1.90	14 : 0 (2.60)
<i>B. accanthoides</i>	11.7	22.5	5.7	1.4650	164	1.3	186	18.60	1.40	25.00	23.70	30.60	22 : 0 (0.60)
<i>M. hamata</i>	6.2	15.9	5.3	1.4582	80	2.0	169	13.92	8.4	31.25	34.97	1.82	20 : 0(4.50), 22 : 0(4.00)
<i>D. cinerea</i>	5.4	16.5	3.8	1.4630	105	2.3	188	14.72	12.12	27.55	36.34	0.97	20 : 0(3.97), 22 : 0(3.66)
<i>A. nervosa</i>	19.2	19.4	4.2	1.4670	103	3.3	200	27.70	10.70	28.70	24.70	6.90	—
<i>C. ternatea</i>	4.9	23.8	4.2	1.4735	150	2.3	185	15.61	5.29	14.28	42.31	16.98	20 : 0(2.24)
<i>T. purpurea</i>	7.1	25.2	4.5	1.4740	142	1.3	187	15.59	4.89	16.35	39.29	15.64	20 : 0(3.11), 22 : 0(4.21)
<i>S. mulayanum</i>	22.3	24.0	2.8	1.4632	147	2.6	121	16.57	2.91	26.81	35.62	16.15	—

major component. Other saturated acids found as minor components were stearic, myristic, arachidic and behenic. Most of the oils examined are of non-drying class except species sl. nos. 6 and 7 which belong to semi-drying class.

C. Viscosa (sl. no. 1) studied earlier by Ahmed *et al.*¹ described the absence of linolenic acid. This acid has been found to be 1.9% in the present investigation. The differences in composition may be attributed to the difference in analytical procedures or ecological factors².

Experimental

Cleaned, dried and powdered seeds were extracted with petroleum ether in a soxhlet apparatus and the extracted oil was neutralized by passing it in chloroform solution, through a short column of alumina. The analytical value of oils and seeds were determined according to the AOCS methods.

Seed oil was refluxed with ethanolic potassium hydroxide. The unsaponifiable material was removed and the free fatty acids were obtained in the usual manner. Wherever necessary, saponification was carried out under nitrogen and samples were stored at low temperature in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Esterification was carried out following the usual proce-

dure, except where specified. In special cases, methyl esters were prepared by well-known transesterification (0.4% sodium methoxide) or by diazomethane procedure.

Electronic spectra (cyclohexane) and IR spectra (film in 1% CCl₄) were recorded on Carl-Zeiss and Specord 75 instrument, respectively. GLC was carried out with a Perkin-Elmer instrument. Methods of sample preparation and TLC procedures etc. were performed according to the standard procedures¹⁻³.

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